

Rapid Medical Evaluation and Treatment in the Emergency Department

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Background

Overcrowding in EDs has become a global concern:

- 130 million ED visits each year. (CDC, 2016)
- Numbers of U.S. EDs decreased. (Wiler, Bolandifar, Griffey, Poirier, & Olsen, 2013).
- Dysfunctional system operations. (Eitel, Rudkin, Malvehy, Killen, & Pines, 2010)
- ↑ elderly patients & complex chronic diseases. (Boagye-Sarfo et al., 2015; Bond et al., 2007)
- Emergency Services exceeds the available resources. (Gordon, Billings, Asplin, & Rhodes, 2001; Schneider, Gallery, Schafermeyer, & Zwemer, 2003).

Significance

ED Overcrowding:

- Threat to public safety.
- Poor quality of care and ↑ inpatient mortality.
- Delayed medical treatment.
- ↓ patient satisfaction & ↑ numbers of patients who left without being seen (LWBS).

(Bernstein et al., 2009; Clarey & Cooke, 2012; Farley & Kwun, 2016; Guttman, Schull, Vermeulen, & Stuke, 2011; Jo et al., 2015; Johnson & Winkelman, 2011; McCusker, Vadeboncoeur, Lévesque, Clampl, & Belzile, 2014; Pines et al., 2011; Singer, Thode, Viccello, & Pines, 2011; B. C. Sun et al., 2013).

Purpose

...to create, design, and implement a RMET process at a community hospital to alleviate ED overcrowding and render timely care.

Objectives

1. ↓ door to provider time (DTP time) to 20 mins or less for ESI IV and V patients.
2. ↓ total length of stay (LOS) in discharged and admitted ED patients.
3. ↓ numbers of patients LWBS.
4. Maintain or improve levels of patient satisfaction as measured by Press Ganey Satisfaction Survey.
5. Track numbers of patients discharged from RMET area post evaluation and treatment.

Framework

Conceptual framework of Input/Throughput/Output-ED workflow. Adapted from "Conceptual Model of Emergency Crowding" by Asplin et al., 2003, *Annals of Emergency Medicine*, 42, p. 176. (Reprinted with permission).

Results

RMET Flowchart

Methods

Design: Pre-post evaluation of RMET
 Setting: 265 bed ED with > 50,000 patient visits/year
 Sample: 85,713 ED patient records (1/2018- 8/2019)
 Measures: DTP time, LOS-D, LOS-A, LWBS, & patient satisfaction
 Analysis: Control charts (I-charts) showing means, upper & lower control limits

Recommendations

- Involve hospital administration in issues related to ED overcrowding.
- Post-implementation data collection and analysis to be done after final construction phase of RMET area in ED (currently in progress).
- Continue RMET process and re-evaluate after 6 months.
- Open excess walk in clinic or schedule same day appointments.
- Identify contributors of patient boarding (*throughput* issue not impacted by RMET).

Conclusions

- ED overcrowding is a multifaceted system-wide problem. (Le & Hsia, 2014; Love et al., 2016; Venkatesh et al., 2015)
- RMET is one strategy to improve throughput, ↑ ED capacity.
- Solutions dependent on hospital culture, size, demographics, hospital leadership engagement, other factors. (Le & Hsia, 2014; Love et al., 2016; Venkatesh et al., 2015)
- Studies have showed positive relationship between improved indicators of quality of care (e.g., DTP time, LOS, LWBS) and overall patient satisfaction. (Begaz et al., 2017; Bullard et al., 2012; Burström et al., 2016; Chartier et al., 2015; French et al., 2014; Lauks et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2013; Milsten et al., 2014; Ming et al., 2016; Raven et al., 2016; Rogg et al., 2013; Rowe et al., 2011; Sorekum et al., 2014; Traub et al., 2016; Weston et al., 2017)

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